

13th INTERNATIONAL
CONGRESS
OF THE SERBIAN SOCIETY
OF TOXICOLOGY

1st TOXSEE
REGIONAL
CONFERENCE

Present and Future of toxicology: Challenges and opportunities

10 - 12 May, 2023 Belgrade

electronic

ABSTRACT
BOOK

www.toxsee2023.com

DEAR COLLEAGUES, DEAR FRIENDS,

We are delighted to greet you on the **13th International Congress of the Serbian Society of Toxicology & 1. TOXSEE Regional Conference - Present and Future of toxicology: challenges and opportunities**, organized in Belgrade from 10-12 May 2023.

Five years after our last international Congress we gathered in Belgrade, to further promote contemporary toxicology, in the broadest sense of meaning, as a response to the new challenges requiring innovative approaches and solutions, as it is understood in the third decade of the XXI century.

Initial concept, to blend the top scientific level in toxicology with the potentials of its' use in broad array of clinical and other domains, proved to be right. Line-up of more than 70 first class international and regional faculties as well as best Serbian scientists and toxicology professionals in all related domains fully justify the approach. Moreover, interest and presence of more than 250 colleagues from Serbia and region witness that our professional community has recognized the approach taken and shown vast interest.

The Serbian Society of Toxicology is committed to innovation and creativity in research and education, in cooperation with collegial associations and institutions in Serbia and abroad. As a regional leader, we developed and inaugurated the regional brand TOXSEE, with the idea to gather as much as possible expertise and know-how from the region and Europe, to capture knowledge, share experience and exchange practical skills with colleagues who deal with toxicology problems daily.

Time imposes on us the need to integrate science, top knowledge and daily practice in a quality and efficient way, to contribute to the better health of the society as a whole in the most purposeful manner. Therefore, a thematic and functional connections with domains of emergency medicine, general medicine, paediatrics, ecology, in addition to already standard toxicological disciplines i.e. clinical, forensic, occupational, and experimental toxicology have been enhanced.

We are glad to host you in a pleasant atmosphere of Belgrade in mid-May, to benefit from the attractive and dynamic program, exchange knowledge, and, equally important, to refresh existing and establish new contacts with colleagues and friends, while enjoying our hospitality and cherish the moment in one of the best partying cities of Europe.

YOU ARE MOST WELCOME!!!

Prof. dr Petar Bulat

- *President of the STC*
- *President of the 13th STC Congress*

Petar Bulat

Prof. dr Biljana Antonijević

- *President of the CSC*
- *of the 13th STC Congress*

B. Antonijević

Prof. dr Predrag Vukomanović

- *President of the COC*
- *of the 13th STC Congress*

P. Vukomanović

SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE

Biljana Antonijević - Serbia / President

Vitomir Ćupić Serbia

Slavica Vučinić Serbia

Milena Kataranovski Serbia

Zorica Bulat Serbia

Vesna Kilibarda Serbia

Aleksandra Buha Đorđević Serbia

Jasmina Jović Stošić Serbia

Dragica Brkić Serbia

Slobodan Nikolić Serbia

Miloš Stojiljković ...Bosna & Hercegovina

Maja Peraica Croatia

Jose E. Manautou USA

Kamil Musilek Czech Republic

Emanuela Corsini Italy

Nursen Basaran Turkey

Metoda Dodić Fikfak Slovenia

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE

Predrag Vukomanović - Serbia / President

Evica Antonijević Miljaković Serbia

Marijana Ćurčić Serbia

Danijela Đukić Ćosić Serbia

Lana Kukobat Serbia

Stefan Mandić Rajčević Serbia

Slavica Milutinović Serbia

Bojana Petrović Serbia

Andrea Pirković Serbia

Branislava Srdenović Čonić ... Serbia

Milena Stošić Serbia

DA LI SU ADOLESCENTI U VOJVODINI IZLOŽENI MEŠAVINI KANCEROGENIH ELEMENATA?

ENDOCRINE
DISRUPTORS

**Nataša Milošević¹, Maja Milanović¹, Kristina Stepanović², Stefan Stojanoski^{3,4},
Sanja Bjelović^{3,5}, Nataša Milić¹, Milica Medić Stojanoska^{2,3}**

1 Univerzitet u Novom Sadu – Medicinski fakultet, Katedra za farmaciju, Novi Sad, **Srbija**

2 Klinika za endokrinologiju, dijabetes i bolesti metabolizma,
Klinički centar Vojvodine, Novi Sad, **Srbija**

3 Univerzitet u Novom Sadu – Medicinski fakultet, Novi Sad, **Srbija**

4 Institut za onkologiju Vojvodine, Sremska Kamenica, **Srbija**

5 Institut za javno zdravlje Vojvodine, Novi Sad, **Srbija**

Arsen i teški metali, kao što su hrom, nikl i kadmijum, su klasifikovani kao kancerogeni elementi. Hronična izloženost ovim elementima povezana je sa povećanjem oksidativnog stresa, inflamacijom i narušavanjem biohemijskih procesa kod ljudi. Naročito vulnerabilna su deca i mlade odrasle osobe. Cilj pilot studije je bio da se utvrdi izloženost adolescenta sa teritorije Vojvodine arsenu, hromu, niklu i kadmijumu.

Metodom slučajnog izbora prikupljeni su uzorci jutarnjeg urina 54 adolescenata oba pola, starosti od 11 do 21 godine. Sadržaj hroma, nikla, arsena i kadmijuma određen je u 1 ml urina, nakon mikrotalasne digestije, indukovano kuplovanom plazmom sa masenom spektrometrijom (ICP-MS). Najčeće detektovan element u analiziranim uzorcima bio je arsen (98,15%), dok je najniža frekvencija detektovanja zabeležena za kadmijum (29,63%). U više od polovine analiziranih uzoraka izmereni su hrom (55,55%) i nikl (51,85%) iznad limita kvantifikacije. Kako bi se utvrdilo da li postoje razlike između dečaka i devojčica u pogledu frekvencije detektovanja analiziranih elemenata, utvrđeno je da su devojčice više izložene hromu (60,00%) i niklu (62,86%) u odnosu na dečake (47,37% i 31,58%, respektivno).

Međutim, kod dečaka, arsen je detektovan u svim uzorcima (100%) a kadmijum u 36,56% uzoraka urina, u poređenju sa devojčicama (97,14% i 28,57% uzoraka urina, respektivno). Dobijeni rezultati ukazuju da su adolescenti sa teritorije Vojvodine izloženi smeši kancerogenih elemenata. S obzirom na to da je arsen sveprisutan u proučavanoj populaciji, neophodne je preduzeti adekvatne mere za njegovu redukciju u životnoj sredini.

KLJUČNE REČI: arsen, hrom, nikl, kadmijum, ICP-MS

ARE ADOLESCENTS IN VOJVODINA EXPOSED TO MIXTURE OF CARCINOGENIC ELEMENTS?

ENDOCRINE
DISRUPTORS

Nataša Milošević¹, Maja Milanović¹, Kristina Stepanović², Stefan Stojanoski^{3,4},
Sanja Bjelović^{3,5}, Nataša Milić¹, Milica Medić Stojanoska^{2,3}

1 University of Novi Sad – Faculty of medicine, Department of pharmacy, Novi Sad, **Serbia**

2 Clinic for endocrinology, diabetes and metabolic diseases,
Clinical center of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, **Serbia**

3 University of Novi Sad – Faculty of medicine, Novi Sad, **Serbia**

4 Oncology institute of Vojvodina, Sremska Kamenica, **Serbia**

5 Institute of public health of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, **Serbia**

Arsenic and heavy metals such as chromium, nickel and cadmium are classified as carcinogenic elements. Chronic exposure to those elements is associated with increased oxidative stress, inflammation and impairment of normal biochemical mechanism in humans. Children and young adults are more vulnerable to adverse effects of toxic elements than adults. Therefore, the goal of this pilot study was to identify if adolescents in Vojvodina are exposed to arsenic, chromium, nickel and cadmium. This cross-sectional study was conducted on 54 healthy adolescents of both genders, aged from 11-21. Chromium, nickel, arsenic and cadmium were determined in 1 mL of morning urine by inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) after the microwave system digestion.

The highest frequency of the detection was obtained for arsenic (98.15%) while cadmium was presented with the lowest incidence in analysed urine samples (29.63%). Chromium and nickel were found in more than half of the collected samples with 55.55% and 51.85% frequency of the detection, respectively. Regarding the gender differences, girls were more exposed to chromium (60.00%) and nickel (62.86%) in comparison with boys (47.37% and 31.58%, respectively). However, in boys, arsenic and cadmium were detected in 100% and 36.56% urine samples, respectively, in compared with girls (97.14% and 28.57% urine samples, respectively). The obtained results confirmed that adolescents are ubiquitously exposed to mixture of carcinogenic elements. Considering that arsenic is omnipresent in the studied population, there is an urgent need for intervention.

KEYWORDS: arsenic, chromium, nickel, cadmium, ICP-MS